

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF DOMPERIDONE MALEATE ORAL DISSOLVING FILMS: INFLUENCE OF POLYMER CONCENTRATION ON IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE

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Article Received on 16 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 06 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 10 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17879090>

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How to cite this Article: How to cite this Article: Dharma Prasad Khanal^{1*}, Dhiraj Chaudhary^{1*}, Deepti Piya Baniya¹, Sabin Shrestha¹, Akhilesh Kumar Shah¹, Prem Paudyal¹. (2025). Development And Characterization of Domperidone Maleate Oral Dissolving Films: Influence of Polymer Concentration on In-Vitro Drug Release. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1976–1992.

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ABSTRACT

Background: The oral mucosa serves as an effective and selective site for systemic drug delivery due to its high permeability and large surface area, facilitating rapid absorption. Additionally, this route avoids the pain associated with injections and allows administration without the need for water, enhancing patient compliance. Domperidone, an antiemetic drug classified under Biopharmaceutics Classification System [BCS] Class-II, has low solubility and high permeability. Mouth-dissolving dosage forms are particularly beneficial for patients with dysphagia, the elderly, paediatric patients, and those undergoing anticancer therapy.

Objectives: The primary objective of this study was to formulate and evaluate a mouth-dissolving film of Domperidone Maleate and investigate the effect of varying polymer concentrations on drug release characteristics.

Methods: Mouth-dissolving films of Domperidone Maleate were prepared using the solvent casting method. Ingredients included Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA), Glycerine, Aspartame, Vanilla flavour, Citric Acid, Cross povidone, Distilled Water,

and Ethanol. The prepared films were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters, including thickness, weight variation, drug content uniformity, percentage elongation, folding

endurance, surface pH, disintegration time, and in vitro drug release. **Results:** All physical parameters such as appearance, weight variation, thickness, disintegration time, pH, percentage elongation, and folding endurance were found within acceptable limits for all five batches. Drug content was also consistent across the batches. Among them, Batch DC-001 demonstrated the most promising results, showing rapid drug release within 2 minutes, with 91.27% to 99.78% of the drug released within 10 minutes. **Conclusion:** The concentration of polymer had a significant impact on drug release. Higher polymer concentrations retarded the release rate, whereas lower concentrations facilitated faster drug release. Additionally, polymer concentration influenced other film properties, including weight, thickness, folding endurance, and disintegration time.

KEYWORDS: Formulation, Mouth Dissolving, Domperidone, Polymer, Drug Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Mouth dissolving films are an oral drug delivery system developed using transdermal patch technology. These thin films, when placed on the tongue or mucosal tissue, are quickly moistened by saliva, leading to rapid disintegration and dissolution, allowing the drug to be absorbed through the oral mucosa.^[1,2,3]

The oral route remains the most preferred method for drug administration due to its ease of use, cost-effectiveness, and high patient compliance. Oral dosage forms are widely utilized because they allow for self-administration, accurate dosing, and avoidance of pain, making them more favourable than other delivery systems. Despite advancements in drug delivery technologies, the oral route continues to be the most effective for achieving systemic drug effects.^[4]

Oral solid dosage forms primarily tablets and capsules make up approximately 60% of all pharmaceutical formulations. However, issues such as dysphagia (difficulty in swallowing), poor bioavailability, and delayed onset of action have driven the development of alternative forms, including parenteral and liquid orals. While parenteral routes are effective, they are invasive and often painful, leading to reduced compliance. Liquid formulations, though easier to swallow, can pose challenges with dosing accuracy.^[5]

A major challenge with traditional tablets and capsules is that they can be difficult to swallow, especially for paediatric, geriatric, and dysphagic patient's conditions estimated to

affect nearly 35% of the general population.^[6] Situations such as motion sickness, allergic reactions, coughing episodes, fear of choking, or lack of water can further hinder swallowing. To overcome these limitations, orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs), also known as fast dissolving tablets (FDTs), were introduced in the early 20th century. These formulations aim to improve bioavailability, provide faster onset of action, and enhance patient compliance, especially among populations with swallowing difficulties.^[6]

Domperidone is a peripheral dopamine receptor antagonist that primarily blocks D2 and D3 dopamine receptors. It enhances the release of prolactin, stimulates gastric peristalsis, and exhibits antiemetic properties. Domperidone is often used to study dopaminergic pathways and as a prokinetic agent to facilitate delayed gastric emptying.^[7]

Its gastrokinetic effects are attributed to its ability to block peripheral dopamine receptors, which enhances esophageal and gastric peristalsis and reduces lower esophageal sphincter pressure. This action accelerates gastric emptying and shortens small bowel transit time.^[8]

Domperidone's^[9] antiemetic activity is due to its antagonism of dopamine receptors in both the gastrointestinal tract and the chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ), a region located just outside the blood-brain barrier. Its high affinity for D2 and D3 receptors in the CTZ makes it effective in preventing nausea and vomiting.^[10]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Ethics approval

The ethical approval for the study protocol was obtained from the Institutional Review Committee of Manmohan Memorial Institute of Health Sciences College MMIHS IRC Ref.no: 852 Approval for the experimental and data collection from Manmohan Memorial Institute of Health Science Lab.

Materials

Domperidone maleate was used as the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API). Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was employed as the film-forming polymer. Aspartame served as a sweetener, while vanilla was incorporated for flavour enhancement. Citric acid was added as a saliva-stimulating agent, and cross-povidone functioned as a super-disintegrant. Glycerol was used as a plasticizer. Solvents included distilled water, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and ethanol.

Methodology

Five different batches of mouth-dissolving films were formulated by varying the concentration of PVA while keeping the API and excipients constant. The detailed batch composition is presented in Table – 1.

Table 1: Composition of different batches of domperidone mouth-dissolving films.

Ingredients	Batch [DC001]	Batch [DC002]	Batch [DC003]	Batch [DC004]	Batch [DC005]
Domperidone maleate (mg)	12.72	12.72	12.72	12.72	12.72
PVA (mg)	18.85	25.14	31.42	37.71	43.99
Aspartame (mg)	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Vanilla (mg)	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Citric Acid (mg)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Cross-povidone (mg)	23.99	23.99	23.99	23.99	23.99
Glycerol (ml)	31.42	31.42	31.42	31.42	31.42
Water (ml)	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
DMSO (ml)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ethanol (ml)	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00

Active Pharmaceutical and Excipient weight Calculation

The API content was calculated based on the dimensions of the casting plate and the desired film size. The diameter of the casting plate was 9 cm, resulting in a total area (A) of 63.64 cm², calculated using the formula $A = \pi r^2$. To produce uniform films of 4 cm² area, the total number of films obtained from a single plate was determined by dividing the plate area by the film area, yielding approximately 15.91 films per plate. Each individual film was designed to contain 12.72 mg of Domperidone maleate. Therefore, the total amount of API required per plate was calculated by multiplying the drug content per film (12.72 mg) by the total number of films (15.91), resulting in 202.3752 mg of Domperidone maleate per batch. Similarly, the polymer weight per film was calculated by dividing the total amount of PVA used in each batch (denoted as N) by 15.91, ensuring uniform distribution of the polymer across each 4 cm² film. This approach allowed consistent loading of both drug and polymer in every film unit.

Analytical Method Development

Determination of Absorption Maxima

Calibration of Domperidone maleate with Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8

Preparation of Stock Solution: 10 mg of Domperidone maleate was dissolved in 10% methanol as co-solvent. The volume was made up to 100 ml with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) to obtain a stock concentration of 0.1 mg/ml (100 µg/ml).

Preparation of Working Solutions: Aliquots of 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20 ml from the stock solution were pipetted into 100 ml volumetric flasks and diluted with phosphate buffer to obtain concentrations of 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20 µg/ml, respectively. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 284 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Domperidone Maleate Mouth Dissolving Films

Polymer Solution Preparation: The specified quantity of PVA was soaked overnight in distilled water to ensure complete hydration.

Addition of Excipients: Vanilla, citric acid, and cross-povidone were added sequentially to the PVA solution and stirred for 2 hours on a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform dispersion.

Preparation of API Solution: Domperidone maleate was dissolved in DMSO in a separate beaker to ensure complete solubilization.

Sweetener and Plasticizer Solution: Aspartame was dissolved in ethanol in another beaker. Glycerol, as a plasticizer, was weighed separately.

Final Mixing: After 2 hours, the solutions from beakers containing API, sweetener, and plasticizer were gradually incorporated into the polymer-excipient mixture under continuous stirring. The mixture was stirred for an additional 1 hour to achieve a homogeneous film-forming solution.

Casting of Films: The solution was allowed to stand for a while to eliminate entrapped air bubbles. The de-aerated solution was cast onto a 9 cm diameter petri dish and dried in a hot air oven at 40°C for 24 hours to ensure complete solvent evaporation.

Film Cutting and Storage: The dried films were carefully peeled off and cut into uniform sizes of 2×2 cm² (4 cm² area). The films were then wrapped in aluminium foils and stored in desiccators for further evaluation.

General appearance

General appearance of the film was observed visually whether it is transparent, semi-transparent or opaque, Surface of the oral film, Colour and Homogeneity.^[11,12]

Thickness

Five films were randomly selected, and their thickness was measured at five distinct points — one at the centre and at each of the four corners using a digital Vernier calliper. The average thickness for each film was then calculated to ensure uniformity across the formulation.

Film Weight variation

Weight variation was evaluated by individually weighing 10 randomly selected films from each batch. The average weight was calculated, and each film's weight was checked for deviations from the mean to ensure uniformity within acceptable limits.^[12]

Percentage Elongation

Percentage elongation refers to the increase in film length under tensile stress just before breaking. Three films from each batch were randomly selected, and their initial lengths were measured. The films were then manually stretched until rupture, and the final lengths were noted. The percentage elongation was calculated as the average increase in length relative to the initial measurement. Elongation was measured by calculating the percentage increase in film length when subjected to tensile stress. The percentage elongation was determined using the formula.^[12]

$$\text{Percentage Elongation} = (\text{Increase in Length} / \text{Initial Length}) \times 100.$$

Folding Endurance

The folding endurance of the prepared films was determined manually by repeatedly folding a strip of the film at the same location until it broke. The number of folds a film could withstand without cracking or breaking was recorded as the folding endurance value.^[12]

Surface pH

To measure the surface pH, the film was placed in a Petri dish and moistened with 5 ml of distilled water. After allowing it to equilibrate for a few minutes, the surface pH was measured by placing the pH meter electrode in direct contact with the moistened film surface, and the reading was taken after stabilization for 1 minute.^[12]

Disintegration Time

The disintegration time of the prepared films was assessed visually by immersing each film in a beaker containing 25 ml of distilled water. Gentle shaking was performed every 10 seconds, and the time taken for complete disintegration of the film was recorded.^[12]

Drug Content Uniformity

To ensure uniform distribution of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) within the films, drug content uniformity was evaluated. A film measuring 2×2 cm² was carefully cut and immersed in a beaker containing 100 ml of phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8). The mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer to ensure complete dissolution of the film. The resulting solution was then filtered through Whatman filter paper to remove any particulate matter. An aliquot of the filtrate was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask, and the volume was adjusted with phosphate buffer. The absorbance of the final solution was measured at 284 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 serving as the blank.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Calibration Curve of Domperidone Maleate in Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8: A calibration curve was plotted with concentration on the x-axis and absorbance on the y-axis. A straight line was obtained, confirming the linearity and validity of the analytical method.

Figure 1: Calibration Curve of Domperidone Maleate in Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8.

Morphological Properties

The morphological characteristics of the domperidone maleate mouth-dissolving films were assessed with respect to transparency, surface smoothness, colour, and homogeneity across various batches. All five formulations (DC001 to DC005) displayed semi-transparent

properties, allowing partial light passage through the films. The surface of each film appeared smooth, free from cracks or surface irregularities. Visually, all batches maintained a uniform hazy white coloration, which is considered suitable for oral film applications. Furthermore, the films exhibited consistent homogeneity, indicating an even distribution of the drug and excipients within the polymeric matrix. No significant variations in morphological attributes were observed among the batches, confirming the reliability and uniformity of the formulation process shown in Table – 2.

Table 2: Morphological Properties.

S.N.	Batch No.	Transparency	Surface of the oral film	Color	Homogeneity
1.	[DC001]	Semi- Transparent	Smooth	Hazy white	Uniform
2.	[DC002]	Semi- Transparent	Smooth	Hazy white	Uniform
3.	[DC003]	Semi- Transparent	Smooth	Hazy white	Uniform
4.	[DC004]	Semi- Transparent	Smooth	Hazy white	Uniform
5.	[DC005]	Semi- Transparent	Smooth	Hazy white	Uniform

Physiochemical Parameters

Table 3: Evaluation of physiochemical parameters of Domperidone film.

Batches	Batch [DC001]	Batch [DC002]	Batch [DC003]	Batch [DC004]	Batch [DC005]
Thickness	0.35±0.03	0.37±0.04	0.38±0.05	0.46±0.03	0.59±0.05
Weight variation	74.60±8.87	91.20±8.23	109.70±18.05	129.70±12.59	146.70±22.55
Percentage Elongation	11.67±0.02	16.67±0.05	20.00±0.05	36.67±0.12	65.00±0.13
Folding Endurance	132±10.19	180±9.87	241±8.21	267±8.28	295±6.48
pH	6.10±0.20	6.05±0.12	6.00±0.1	5.76±0.15	6.00±0.05
Disintegration time	57±5.56	63±2.08	105±10	127±8.62	143±13.65
Uniformity of content	92.12±0.03	89.88±0.03	87.54±0.02	93.93±0.05	103.06±0.07

Thickness Measurement

The thickness of the films was measured using a micrometre screw gauge or calibrated digital Vernier callipers. Measurements were taken at five different points on each film one at the centre and one at each of the four corners and the mean thickness was calculated. Ensuring uniformity in film thickness is crucial, as it directly influences the accuracy of the drug dose per unit area. Among the prepared batches, the maximum thickness was observed in Batch DC002 (0.592 mm), while the minimum was recorded in Batch DC001 (0.356 mm). Overall, the film thickness ranged from 0.356 mm to 0.592 mm. This variation in thickness is

attributed to differences in PVA concentration, with higher polymer content resulting in thicker films. A similar trend was also reported by Thorat et al.^[13], where an increase in pullulan concentration led to a proportional increase in film thickness shown in Table – 3.

Film Weight Variation

The weight of the mouth-dissolving films was determined using an analytical balance, and the average weight was calculated for each formulation. It is essential that the films exhibit minimal weight variation to ensure uniform distribution of both the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and excipients, thereby maintaining dose accuracy. The observed film weights ranged from 74.6 mg to 146.7 mg across the different batches. An increase in polymer concentration corresponded to a gradual increase in film weight. Batch DC001 exhibited the lowest weight at 74.6 mg, while Batch DC005 showed the highest weight at 146.7 mg shown in Table – 3.

Percentage Elongation

The percentage elongation of the films was determined by measuring the increase in length after applying tensile stress. It was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage Elongation} = [(L - L_0) / L_0] \times 100,$$

Where L represents the final length after stretching, and L_0 is the initial length of the film.

Among the batches, Batch DC005 exhibited the highest percentage elongation of 65%, while Batch DC001 showed the lowest elongation at 11.67%. The increase in elongation with higher PVA concentration is attributed to the plasticizing effect of the polymer, which enhances the film's flexibility and elasticity. This observation is consistent with findings reported by Patel JG et al.^[14], where a rise in PVA content resulted in an increase in film elongation due to enhanced polymeric chain interactions and flexibility shown in Table – 3.

Folding Endurance

Mouth-dissolving films must possess adequate strength and flexibility to withstand mechanical stresses during processing, packaging, transportation, and handling. Folding endurance is a critical parameter to evaluate the film's elasticity and mechanical durability. It was assessed by repeatedly folding a 2 × 2 cm strip of the film at the same location until it broke. The number of folds a film could endure without cracking or breaking was recorded as its folding endurance. All measurements were performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy and

consistency. The folding endurance of the films ranged from 132 folds to 295 folds across the batches. Results indicated that an increase in polymer (PVA) concentration led to a corresponding increase in folding endurance, enhancing the film's mechanical strength and flexibility. Batch DC001, which contained a lower concentration of polymer, exhibited folding endurance values comparable to the N6 formulation reported by Kumara Varma N et al.^[15], demonstrating similar film resilience at equivalent polymer levels shown in Table – 3.

pH Determination

The pH of the films was determined by dissolving a single oral film in 10 ml of distilled water, followed by measuring the pH of the resulting solution using a calibrated pH meter. All measurements were performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy and consistency. It is essential for the films to maintain a uniform pH value to prevent irritation of the buccal mucosa. The pH of the films was found to range between 5.76 and 6.1, which is near neutral. This indicates a minimal risk of mucosal irritation, enhancing patient comfort upon administration. Similar pH ranges were reported by Kumar Varma N. et al.^[15], confirming the suitability of the formulation for buccal delivery shown in Table – 3.

Disintegration Time

The in-vitro disintegration time of the films was evaluated by placing each film in a glass beaker containing 25 ml of distilled water. The solution was gently swirled at 10-second intervals, and the time at which the film began to disintegrate or break apart was recorded as the disintegration time. This test was performed in triplicate for accuracy. Although official Pharmacopoeial standards for orodispersible films (ODFs) are not defined, the disintegration time criteria for orodispersible tablets, typically ranging from 30 seconds to 3 minutes, are often adopted for ODFs. In this study, the disintegration time of the films ranged from 57 seconds to 143 seconds. Batch DC005 exhibited the longest disintegration time at 143 seconds, while Batch DC001 disintegrated the fastest at 57 seconds. This variation is attributed to differences in polymer concentration, where higher polymer content led to prolonged disintegration. A similar trend was reported by Thorat et al.^[16], where increasing the concentration of pullulan resulted in longer disintegration times shown in Table – 3.

Content Uniformity

A 2×2 cm² film was cut and dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8) under continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer to ensure complete dissolution. The resulting solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper and an aliquot was transferred to a 10 ml

volumetric flask, with the volume adjusted to mark using the same buffer. The absorbance of the prepared solution was measured at 284 nm against phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) as a blank using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The results demonstrated that the content uniformity of Domperidone maleate in the films met the required standards, indicating uniform distribution of the drug throughout the film matrix. Similar findings were reported by Deepak *et al.*, where all formulation batches complied with content uniformity specifications shown in Table – 3.

In-vitro Drug Release

The in-vitro drug release studies were performed using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) as the dissolution medium. Film strips containing Domperidone maleate equivalent to 5 mg of drug were carefully placed in the dissolution vessel. The study was conducted using a USP Type II (paddle) dissolution apparatus, operated at a speed of 50 rpm and maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. A total volume of 900 ml phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) was used as the dissolution medium. At predetermined time intervals, aliquots of the dissolution medium were withdrawn, filtered, and analysed spectrophotometrically at 284 nm to determine the amount of drug released. Fresh dissolution medium was replenished after each sampling to maintain sink conditions throughout the study.

Table 4: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC001.

Time (min)	%Drug release (S1)	%Drug release (S2)	%Drug release (S3)	%Drug release (S4)	%Drug release (S5)	%Drug Release (S6)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	71.31	55.60	63.45	41.53	54.94	45.13
4	85.05	76.22	74.58	51.34	64.11	54.94
6	89.96	83.74	85.05	62.80	70.98	66.73
8	95.85	88.98	93.56	81.13	85.05	89.31
10	98.47	91.27	99.78	93.56	94.87	97.49

Figure 2: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC001.

The cumulative drug release was found to be rapid within the first 2 minutes, ranging from 41.53% to 71.31%. Similarly, after 10 minutes, the drug release increased significantly, reaching between 91.28% and 99.79%.

Table 5: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC002.

Time (min)	%Drug release (S1)	%Drug release (S2)	%Drug release (S3)	%Drug release (S4)	%Drug release (S5)	%Drug Release (S6)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	34.65	39.89	31.38	29.42	32.04	39.24
4	55.60	62.80	52.98	52.33	58.22	62.14
6	69.08	73.34	61.56	67.77	64.50	69.41
8	81.78	88.98	77.20	81.13	76.22	89.31
10	91.60	96.84	87.02	93.89	89.31	98.14

Figure 3: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC002.

The cumulative drug release at 2 minutes ranged from 29.42% to 39.24%. In comparison, the release at 10 minutes was between 87.02% and 98.18%, which was comparable to Batch DC001. However, the initial release at 2 minutes was lower than that observed for Batch DC001.

Table 6: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC003.

Time (min)	%Drug release (S1)	%Drug release (S2)	%Drug release (S3)	%Drug release (S4)	%Drug release (S5)	%Drug Release (S6)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	29.74	21.24	25.49	25.82	27.13	21.89
4	62.14	45.78	54.94	58.54	59.85	52.98
6	75.56	62.47	60.84	74.58	72.94	66.07
8	85.71	69.34	71.96	86.04	82.76	78.51
10	87.67	86.69	85.05	89.31	84.07	81.13

Figure 4: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC003.

At the 2-minute mark, the drug release ranged from 21.24% to 29.75%, which was significantly lower compared to Batch DC001. Likewise, the cumulative release at 10 minutes was between 81.13% and 89.31%.

Table 7: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC004.

Time (min)	%Drug release (S1)	%Drug release (S2)	%Drug release (S3)	%Drug release (S4)	%Drug release (S5)	%Drug Release (S6)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	28.11	27.78	27.45	26.80	28.44	26.47
4	51.02	35.96	36.29	45.78	42.51	38.91
6	72.62	72.29	70.98	71.96	71.64	69.02
8	80.47	75.56	78.18	78.51	78.84	74.58
10	83.42	80.14	86.36	86.69	84.07	89.96

Figure 5: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC004.

The drug release at 2 minutes ranged between 26.48% and 28.44%, while at 10 minutes, it increased to a range of 80.15% to 89.97%.

Table 8: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC005.

Time (min)	%Drug release (S1)	%Drug release (S2)	%Drug release (S3)	%Drug release (S4)	%Drug release (S5)	%Drug Release (S6)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	21.84	25.49	26.47	22.87	25.16	26.80
4	33.67	45.13	36.94	32.69	34.00	37.27
6	49.71	56.58	58.54	49.05	52.33	58.87
8	52.98	66.07	69.34	52.33	63.13	68.36
10	71.96	71.31	73.93	68.36	74.25	77.53

Figure 6: Cumulative % drug release of Batch DC005.

The drug release at 2 minutes ranged from 21.84% to 26.80%, while at 10 minutes, it increased to 68.37% to 77.53%. Observing the release pattern across batches, it was evident that the drug release rate gradually decreased with each successive batch after Batch DC001 by the end of the 10-minute interval.

The cumulative in-vitro drug release of Domperidone maleate as a function of time was evaluated for all batches. The results indicated that Batch DC001 exhibited the highest drug release profile. In Batch DC001, a rapid release was observed within the first 2 minutes, and by 10 minutes, 91.27% to 99.78% of the drug had been released. In contrast, the subsequent batches demonstrated a slower release rate, with Batch DC005 showing the lowest release, where only 71.36% to 73.93% of the drug was released within 10 minutes. This inverse relationship between polymer concentration and drug release aligns with findings reported by Pankaj C. Chougule *et al.*^[17], who observed that formulations with lower polymer concentrations exhibited faster and higher drug release compared to those with higher polymer content.

Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was selected as the dissolution medium to simulate the oral cavity environment, as the average pH of human saliva is approximately 6.8. Previous studies have also reported rapid disintegration times with optimized formulations. For instance, oral dissolving films (ODFs) formulated using naturally occurring water-soluble polysaccharides like Pullulan, HPMC E15, and PEG-400 exhibited excellent disintegration within 2 minutes. Similarly, another study reported ODFs prepared with β -cyclodextrin, HPMC E15, and PEG 400-based solid dispersion of Domperidone, achieving disintegration within 70 seconds. Furthermore, varying concentrations of the same polymer (HPMC E15) demonstrated that lower polymer concentrations resulted in a higher cumulative drug release, which is consistent with the observations in this study.^[17]

CONCLUSION

Mouth dissolving films (ODFs) of Domperidone maleate were successfully formulated using the solvent casting method and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters. The results demonstrated that the formulations complied with the quality standards set by the Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) using validated analytical methods. It was observed that increasing the concentration of polymer (PVA) led to an increase in disintegration time, while folding endurance decreased, highlighting the critical role of polymer concentration in film performance. Among the prepared batches, Batch DC001 exhibited superior drug release and disintegration characteristics, suggesting its potential as an optimized formulation for further in-vivo evaluation and clinical studies.

Limitations

Despite the successful formulation and evaluation, the study had certain limitations. Only a single polymer (PVA) was utilized, which may limit the mechanical flexibility and cost-effectiveness of the formulation. Additionally, the study was restricted to in-vitro evaluations, and no in-vivo bioavailability or pharmacokinetic studies were conducted to validate the clinical efficacy of the formulated films. The solvent casting method, although effective for laboratory-scale production, may require modifications and process optimization for large-scale commercial manufacturing.

Recommendations

For future research, it is recommended to explore combinations of PVA with other cost-effective and natural polymers to improve the mechanical strength, disintegration time, and overall economic feasibility of the ODFs. Incorporating super-disintegrants or plasticizers in

optimized concentrations may further enhance film performance. Moreover, in-vivo studies should be conducted to establish the pharmacokinetic profile and patient acceptability of the developed formulations. Scaling up the production process with appropriate modifications is also essential for potential commercial application.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors sincerely thank the Department of Pharmacy at Manmohan Memorial Institute of Health Sciences, and our deep sense of gratitude to Arrow Pharmaceutical Private Limited, Maha Manjushree Nagarkot, for their invaluable support and encouragement throughout the research process.

Funding

No funding available.

Conflicts Of Interest

No conflicts of interest are to be declared.

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